

Global machine learning potentials for molecular crystals

Ivan Žugec,¹ R. Matthias Geilhufe,² and Ivor Lončarić^{3, a)}

¹⁾*Centro de Física de Materiales CFM/MPC (CSIC-UPV/EHU), Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain*

²⁾*Department of Physics, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden*

³⁾*Ruder Bošković Institute, Bijenička 54, Zagreb, Croatia*

Molecular crystals are difficult to model with accurate first principles methods due to the large unit cells. On the other hand, accurate modeling is required as polymorphs often differ by only 1 kJ/mol. Machine learning interatomic potentials promise to provide accuracy of baseline first principles methods with orders of magnitude lower cost. Using existing databases of density functional theory calculations for molecular crystals and molecules, we train global machine learning interatomic potentials, usable for any molecular crystal. We test the performance of the potentials on experimental benchmarks and show that they perform better than classical force fields and in some cases can perform comparable to density functional theory calculations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Molecular crystals are ubiquitous materials that find many uses, from electronics^{1,2}, to the pharmaceutical industry^{3,4}. Atomistic modeling of molecular crystals relies either on (tailor-made) classical interatomic potentials (force fields) or density functional theory (DFT). Force fields are orders of magnitude faster than DFT, but often are not accurate enough. DFT offers the best accuracy and computational complexity ratio for most materials' (ground state) properties. However, due to the large average unit cell of molecular crystals, DFT is computationally expensive. Furthermore, molecular crystals show strong electronic correlations, due to weak intermolecular electron hopping, resulting in a suppressed kinetic energy. While this gives rise to interesting many-body instabilities⁵⁻⁸, it often requires computationally expensive approaches such as hybrid functionals.

In recent years, machine learning interatomic potentials (MLIPs) have promised to provide the best of both worlds, speed comparable to force fields, and accuracy similar to the baseline DFT data. MLIPs have been successfully used to model many different materials and their properties, see reviews⁹⁻¹³. Even better, based on very large databases with millions of entries, such as Materials Project¹⁴, recent MLIPs¹⁵⁻¹⁷ cover the whole periodic table and, in principle, can be used for any material. However, current large DFT databases, such as Materials Project¹⁴, AFLOW¹⁸, OQMD¹⁹, and NOMAD²⁰, are concentrated on inorganic materials due to their relatively small average unit cell. The average unit cell in the Materials project of ~ 28 atoms is much smaller than the average unit cell of molecular crystal in the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)²¹ of >200 . Therefore, current global MLIPs do not cover the configurational space of molecular crystals.

Present DFT databases for molecular crystals are relatively small. To the best of our knowledge, the largest database is the Organic Materials Database

(OMDB)²²⁻²⁵ which contains electronic structure calculations (bandstructure and density of states) of 40,948 organic molecular crystals and metalorganic framework materials. Several thousand structures are also calculated in ShiftML databases focusing on NMR chemical shifts²⁶. On the other hand, extensive databases exist for DFT calculations of molecules. The largest example is ANI-1^{27,28} database with over 20 million conformations of small molecules. While crystal databases are calculated with semilocal DFT, molecular databases are often calculated with more accurate hybrid functionals.

The main idea of this work is to explore the possibility of creating a global MLIP - valid for any molecular crystal - trained on the existing databases, such as OMDB and ANI-1x²⁹, and test it on predicting properties of molecular crystals. This is a bold idea as OMDB is likely too small to generalize over the whole configurational space of molecular crystals, and molecular datasets are not made to sample intermolecular interactions existing in molecular crystals.

In general, MLIPs have not been widely applied to molecular crystals. This has to do with the fact that MLIPs are often short-ranged and long-range interactions such as dispersion and electrostatics are essential in molecular crystals. Some of the existing MLIP applications on molecular crystals did not correct for the long-range interactions. Still, it was shown that pentacene and azapentacene potential can be machine-learned to sub-kJ·mol⁻¹ accuracy³⁰. MLIPs were also used to calculate Gibbs free energies for several molecular crystals and predict thermodynamic stability in agreement with experiments^{31,32}. Even these few studies show that some properties of particular molecular crystals can be accurately modeled with short-ranged MLIPs. The only study of molecular crystals incorporating long-range interactions was the delta machine learning method for short-range interactions on top of density functional tight binding baseline providing long-range electrostatics^{33,34}.

The inception of Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials (MLIPs) can be traced back to the pioneering work of Behler and Parrinello, who employed simple feed-forward neural networks and Gaussian symmetry functions as descriptors³⁵. Another influential early contri-

^{a)}Electronic mail: ivor.loncaric@gmail.com

bution utilized more sophisticated descriptors and Gaussian process regression³⁶. Subsequent advancements in the field have largely followed either the neural network or kernel-based approach^{9–13}. To achieve the overarching goal of constructing a global MLIP applicable to any molecular crystal, neural network methodologies are preferred due to their evaluation cost independence from the quantity of training data—a necessity when covering the vast configurational space of molecular crystals. While initial neural network architectures, like Behler-Parrinello, relied on manually crafted descriptors, contemporary top-performing networks adopt end-to-end architectures that eliminate the need for predefined descriptors³⁷. These models typically represent the atomic structure as a graph, where edges connect two atoms (nodes) within a specified cutoff distance. Subsequent convolution or message-passing operations on this graph are employed to glean the atomic environment’s representation for each atom.

In the present contribution, we show that our end-to-end MLIPs when benchmarked with experimentally determined structures and formation energies, show accuracy better than force fields and, in some cases, comparable to DFT. In particular, we show that molecular datasets with few molecular dimers already allow for reasonable global MLIP for molecular crystals. While our open and ready-to-use models can be already used for different applications, we propose how to further improve the accuracy of our models.

II. METHODS

In this section, we present details about datasets and models used in this work.

A. Datasets

We used two datasets for training MLIPs, the ANI-1x²⁹ and the OMDB²². Both datasets contain information about the energy of the system and forces on all atoms. As a preprocessing step, we subtracted the atomic self-energies for each dataset, which established a consistent energy baseline. This step aids in isolating bonding energies from the inherent atomic energies, ensuring comparability across diverse training sets. For benchmarking prediction accuracy of trained models on molecular crystals we used the CSD-2k²⁶ and X23 datasets³⁸.

1. ANI-1x

ANI-1x²⁹ is a subset of a larger ANI-1²⁷ dataset obtained by means of active learning via query by committee. It contains a variety of different structures including off-equilibrium organic molecules, dimers, and structures obtained by ab initio molecular dynamics. All structures

within the ANI-1x are composed of C, H, N, and O atoms. The DFT calculations were performed with the hybrid ω B97X exchange-correlation functional³⁹ and the 6–31 G(d) basis set⁴⁰. For training MLIPs, we have randomly split the ANI-1x dataset into 4,567,229 training configurations and 50,000 validation configurations.

2. OMDB

OMDB²³ provides single-point DFT calculations for experimental structures of molecular crystals. In this work, we use a subset of 10 788 crystals that contain only C, H, N, and O atoms with an average number of atoms in the unit cell being 82. All calculations in OMDB were performed with PBE exchange-correlation functional⁴¹. For training MLIPs, we have randomly split the dataset to 9298 training configurations and 490 validation configurations.

3. X23

The X23 dataset^{38,42} is a standard benchmarking dataset for molecular crystals and has established itself as an important benchmark for evaluating the accuracy of dispersion interactions. It includes accurate experimental lattice energies and volumes for 23 small to medium-sized molecular crystals with 12–72 atoms in the unit cell. The dataset covers van der Waals-bonded, hydrogen-bonded, and mixed molecular crystals. For all comparisons, we use the revised X23 dataset³⁸ that accounts for the effect of thermal expansion.

4. CSD-2k

CSD-61k dataset²⁶ comprises all crystals from the CSD containing C, H, N, and O atoms and having less than 200 atoms. CSD-2k dataset is then additionally filtered from the original CSD-61k by means of a farthest point sampling algorithm^{43,44} to 2 000 structures, ensuring near-uniform sampling of conformational space.

B. MLIP architectures and models

1. NequIP

NequIP architecture, based on E(3)-Equivariant Neural Networks⁴⁵, is designed to efficiently learn the interatomic potential of molecules and materials. The important hyperparameters that were chosen for NequIP trained on ANI-1x and OMDB were identical unless stated otherwise (further details, including model configurations, are available in supporting data). The cutoff radius was set to 5 Å, the number of interaction and radial layers were set to 4 and 2 respectively, while the

maximum rotation order was set to 2. The batch size was equal to 128 for ANI1-x and 8 for OMDb. The loss function was a mean square error function of both energy and force normalized by the total number of atoms. Weight coefficients for both energy of force were chosen to be equal to unity. The learning rate was regulated by Pytorch’s implementation of the ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler with patience being equal to 6 and a decay factor of 0.5. Validation energy MAEs per atom are 2.8 meV and 6.3 meV while validation forces MAEs are 47 meV/Å and 48 meV/Å on ANI-1x and OMDb, respectively.

2. ANI-2x

ANI-2x model is an ensemble of 8 pre-trained neural networks trained on a ANI-2x dataset⁴⁶ which extends ANI-1x with structures containing F, Cl and S. The set of these 7 elements (C, H, N, O, F, Cl, S) make up $\sim 90\%$ of drug-like molecules. Additionally, ANI-2x underwent torsional refinement training to better predict molecular torsion profile.

C. Calculation details

All calculations have been performed in the Atomic Simulation Environment (ASE)⁴⁷. Positions of atoms and unit cells of each crystal were relaxed until forces on each atom was smaller than 5×10^{-4} eV/Å keeping the symmetry of the experimental structure.

Since MLIPs were trained on datasets calculated with either ω B97X or PBE exchange-correlation functional, all predictions can be afterwards corrected for van der Waals interactions. We have used D4 correction^{48,49} that is convenient as it does not depend on DFT charge densities. We have used D4 parameters corresponding to the respective baseline exchange-correlation functional.

III. RESULTS

As a first benchmark of global MLIPs for molecular crystals we test them on lattice energies from revisited X23³⁸ dataset. Fig. 1 shows a comparison of predictions of selected MLIPs and corrected experimental values.

All studied MLIPs show reasonable predictions for most if not all of the crystals in the X23 dataset. The least consistent predictions are obtained by the ANI2x+D4 model which shows a very high overestimation of lattice energy for CO₂ and s-Triazine while models using Nequip architecture perform better. In Table I we show a statistical comparison of the performance of different MLIPs as well as various force fields and DFT approximations. The best-performing global MLIP is the Nequip model trained on the ANI-1x dataset (Nequip@ANI1x), followed by the Nequip

FIG. 1. X23 lattice energies compared to MLIPs predictions.

Model/Energy Model	MA%D	MAD	ME	SD
Nequip@ANI1x	9.90	0.09	-0.03	0.12
Nequip@ANI1x+D4	29.19	0.24	-0.24	0.11
ANI2x	37.31	0.23	0.06	0.34
ANI2x+D4	33.65	0.19	-0.05	0.33
Nequip@OMDB	66.36	0.57	0.57	0.20
Nequip@OMDB+D4	15.41	0.13	0.11	0.10
<hr/>				
FIT ⁵⁰	10.27	0.10	-0.08	0.09
W99rev6311P ⁵⁰	15.72	0.15	-0.15	0.10
W99rev6311P3 ⁵⁰	16.79	0.16	-0.16	0.11
W99_DMA ⁵⁰	17.47	0.16	-0.16	0.12
W99rev6311 ⁵⁰	18.28	0.17	-0.17	0.11
W99_ESP ⁵⁰	25.27	0.23	-0.22	0.14
<hr/>				
GFN-FF-Orig. ⁵¹	38.95	0.30	0.28	0.17
GFN-FF-W ⁵¹	37.03	0.29	0.26	0.19
GFN-FF-dATM ⁵¹	30.60	0.24	0.20	0.18
GFN-FF-W+dATM ⁵¹	28.34	0.22	0.18	0.18
<hr/>				
TPSS-D3 ⁵²	4.64	0.04	-0.00	0.04
PBE-D3 ⁵²	4.42	0.04	-0.01	0.05
HSE06-D3 ⁵²	5.18	0.04	-0.02	0.04
PBE-XDM ^{53 a}	8.09	0.07	0.03	0.08
PBE-MBD ⁴²	6.89	0.06	-0.04	0.05

^a Evaluated on C21 dataset

TABLE I. Comparative analysis of Mean Absolute Relative Deviation (MA%D), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD, eV), Mean Error (ME, eV), and Standard Deviation (SD, eV) of revised X23³⁸ lattice energy for MLIPs, force fields, and multiple dispersion-corrected DFT calculations.

model trained on OMDb supplemented with D4 correction (Nequip@OMDB+D4). D4 correction is essential for the PBE-based OMDb model, which significantly underestimated lattice energy and performed the poorest among models when used without the D4 correction.

ANI2x on average slightly underestimates lattice energy and ANI2x+D4 slightly overestimates lattice energy, but both have significant deviations. Interestingly, D4 correction worsens results when used on the Nequip@ANI1x model by consistently making predicted lattice energy too negative.

The MLIPs’ performance can be compared to the performance of force fields and DFT. For force fields, we have selected two different classes, tailor-made force fields for each molecule in the dataset (FIT and W99) and general force fields (GFN-FF). We have also selected different exchange-correlation approximations in DFT, ranging from semi-local to hybrid functionals supplemented with different van der Waals corrections. Best-performing global MLIPs are performing much better than general force fields and on par or better than tailor-made force fields in predicting lattice energies. VdW corrected DFT is superior showing around twice as good performance.

Next, we benchmark MLIPs on volume predictions from the X23 dataset as shown in Fig. 2 and Table II. Again, MLIPs predict volumes well in most

FIG. 2. Relative difference of MLIP predictions and X23 volumes.

cases, except for CO_2 which is not modelled well with ANI2x+D4 and Nequip@OMDB+D4. Best performing model for volumes is Nequip@ANI1x+D4 followed by Nequip@OMDB+D4 and Nequip@ANI1x. D4 correction is essential for OMDB-based models also for predicting volumes. Compared to force fields, global MLIPs perform better than tailor-made force fields and significantly better than general force fields. Global MLIPs are also competitive with DFT for volume predictions as best global MLIPs show slightly smaller deviations and smaller mean errors.

Small X23 dataset is suitable for benchmarking computationally heavy DFT calculations or laborious tailor-made force fields, but general MLIPs are both fast and

Model/Energy Model	MAD	ME	SD
Nequip@ANI1x	5.05	2.81	5.09
Nequip@ANI1x+D4	4.13	1.05	4.83
ANI2x	8.59	5.44	10.33
ANI2x+D4	8.07	4.67	10.19
Nequip@OMDB	31.6	31.6	35.56
Nequip@OMDB+D4	6.14	2.9	11.09
<hr/>			
FIT ⁵⁰ a	6.22	3.94	7.08
W99rev6311P5 ⁵⁰ a	8.03	7.54	4.94
<hr/>			
GFN-FF-Orig. ⁵¹	11.39	-10.3	7.84
GFN-FF-W ⁵¹	12.15	-11.04	7.71
GFN-FF-dATM ⁵¹	11.37	-10.24	7.73
GFN-FF-W+dATM ⁵¹	12.02	-10.89	7.69
<hr/>			
TPSS-D3 ⁵²	6.37	2.11	11.44
PBE-D3 ⁵²	6.99	2.84	11.02
PBE-XDM ⁵³ b	14.3	13.1	7.84
PBE-MBD ⁴²	5.07	5.07	2.71

^a Urea excluded from analysis.

^b Evaluated on C21 dataset

TABLE II. Comparative analysis of Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD, %), Mean Error (ME, %), and Standard Deviation (SD, %) of relative error of unit cell volumes on X23 dataset³⁸ for MLIPs, force fields, and dispersion-corrected DFT calculations.

easy to use and can be also efficiently used on larger benchmarking datasets. We used the CSD-2k dataset of the most diverse crystals with unit cells containing less than 200 atoms to benchmark MLIP predictions for structures. Fig. 3 shows histograms of relative volume differences between MLIPs predictions and experimental values. Statistical analysis is given in Table

FIG. 3. caption.

III. For CSD-2k, thermal expansion correction was not applied so a few percent difference is possible even for the perfect model. A recent survey of thermal expansion data in CSD calculated the mean expansion coefficient to be $168 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-154}$, so the expected aver-

Model/Energy Model	MAD	ME	SD	RE \geq 20 %
Nequip@ANI1x	4.44	-1.44	6.57	1.39
Nequip@ANI1x+D4	5.2	-3.64	5.57	1.37
ANI2x	6.36	1.86	9.64	4.22
ANI2x+D4	6.15	0.95	9.34	3.83
Nequip@OMDB	19.66	19.51	14.58	34.65
Nequip@OMDB+D4	5.7	-4.16	5.51	1.37

TABLE III. Comparative analysis of Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD, %), Mean Error (ME, %), Standard Deviation (SD, %), and portion of crystals with difference in volume larger than 20% (RE \geq 20 %, %) for machine learning potentials with respect to the volumes extracted from CSD-2k dataset²⁶.

age difference between volume predictions at $T = 0$ and $T = 300$ K, would be -5% . Best performing models on X23 volumes, Nequip@ANI1x, Nequip@ANI1x+D4, and Nequip@OMDB+D4 are also performing well on a CSD-2k dataset. As one would expect, they show a few percent negative mean and small deviations, similar to deviations in X23. ANI-2x and ANI-2x+D4 predict positive mean while Nequip@OMDB again gives worst results with large mean error.

Table III also includes information on the percentage of volume predictions that are more than 20% different than experiments. We use this as a measure of the portion of structures for which MLIPs completely failed. Good-performing models have only $\sim 1\%$ of such structures, while it is more than 30% in the case of the worst-performing model.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have explored the possibility of creating global MLIPs for molecular crystals that would provide accurate, fast, and effortless substitution for expensive DFT-based approaches or laborious and inaccurate tailor-made force fields. Available datasets for training such MLIPs are not ideal as current databases of molecular crystals are small compared to the configurational space, and large databases exist only for molecular systems which do not cover all intramolecular interactions existing in crystals.

We show that modern end-to-end MLIP architectures such as Nequip, even when trained on nonideal databases perform better than (tailor-made) force fields both for energy and structure predictions. DFT is superior for energy predictions showing performance that is two times better on X23 metrics, but performance on volume predictions is similar. As our models work reasonably well with far-from-ideal databases, our work demonstrates that as the training databases improve, including more configurations relevant to molecular crystals, global MLIPs will become even more accurate.

The good performance of MLIPs is rather surprising as it is well known that long-range interactions, such as elec-

trostatics and dispersion, are essential for molecular crystals, and the interaction range to reach convergence can extend to tens of angstroms⁵⁵, while our MLIPs are relatively short-ranged. Machine learning models can also uncontrollably fail. We show that in $\sim 1\%$ of relaxations, predicted volumes are off by more than 20%, showing that improvements in global MLIPs for molecular crystals are not only possible but also needed. Nevertheless, our ready-to-use models can be already used for different tasks such as structural relaxations, free energy corrections, or crystal structure prediction⁵⁶, by partially or fully replacing expensive DFT calculations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported in part by Croatian Science Foundation under the project UIP-2020-02-5675. RMG acknowledges support from the Swedish Research Council (VR Starting Grant No. 2022-03350) and Chalmers University of Technology, via the Department of Physics and the Areas of Advance Nano and Materials.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Ivan Žugec: Data Curation (equal); Formal Analysis (lead); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing/Original Draft Preparation (equal); Writing/Review & Editing (equal). R. Matthias Geilhufe: Data Curation (equal); Writing/Review & Editing (equal). Ivor Lončarić: Conceptualization (lead); Funding Acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Project Administration (lead); Resources (lead); Software (equal); Supervision (lead); Writing/Original Draft Preparation (equal); Writing/Review & Editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10462367>, reference number 10462368.

¹S. R. Forrest, "The path to ubiquitous and low-cost organic electronic appliances on plastic," *Nature* **428**, 911–918 (2004).

²M. Muccini, "A bright future for organic field-effect transistors," *Nature Materials* **5**, 605–613 (2006).

³L. S. Taylor, D. E. Braun, and J. W. Steed, "Crystals and Crystallization in Drug Delivery Design," *Molecular Pharmaceutics* **18**, 751–753 (2021).

- ⁴N. K. Duggirala, M. L. Perry, Ö. Almarsson, and M. J. Zaworotko, “Pharmaceutical cocrystals: along the path to improved medicines,” *Chemical Communications* **52**, 640–655 (2016).
- ⁵Y. Shimizu, K. Miyagawa, K. Kanoda, M. Maesato, and G. Saito, “Spin liquid state in an organic mott insulator with a triangular lattice,” *Physical Review Letters* **91**, 107001 (2003).
- ⁶S. Brown, “Organic superconductors: The bechgaard salts and relatives,” *Physica C: Superconductivity and its Applications* **514**, 279–289 (2015).
- ⁷M. Hirata, K. Ishikawa, K. Miyagawa, M. Tamura, C. Berthier, D. Basko, A. Kobayashi, G. Matsuno, and K. Kanoda, “Observation of an anisotropic dirac cone reshaping and ferrimagnetic spin polarization in an organic conductor,” *Nature communications* **7**, 12666 (2016).
- ⁸R. M. Geilhufe and B. Olsthoorn, “Identification of strongly interacting organic semimetals,” *Physical Review B* **102**, 205134 (2020).
- ⁹V. L. Deringer, M. A. Caro, and G. Csányi, “Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials as Emerging Tools for Materials Science,” *Advanced Materials* **31** (2019), 10.1002/adma.201902765.
- ¹⁰B. Mortazavi, X. Zhuang, T. Rabczuk, and A. V. Shapeev, “Atomistic modeling of the mechanical properties: the rise of machine learning interatomic potentials,” *Materials Horizons* **10**, 1956–1968 (2023).
- ¹¹O. T. Unke, S. Chmiela, H. E. Sauceda, M. Gastegger, I. Poltavsky, K. T. Schütt, A. Tkatchenko, and K.-R. Müller, “Machine Learning Force Fields,” *Chemical Reviews* **121**, 10142–10186 (2021).
- ¹²J. A. Keith, V. Vassilev-Galindo, B. Cheng, S. Chmiela, M. Gastegger, K.-R. Müller, and A. Tkatchenko, “Combining Machine Learning and Computational Chemistry for Predictive Insights Into Chemical Systems,” *Chemical Reviews* **121**, 9816–9872 (2021).
- ¹³F. Musil, A. Grisafi, A. P. Bartók, C. Ortner, G. Csányi, and M. Ceriotti, “Physics-Inspired Structural Representations for Molecules and Materials,” *Chemical Reviews* **121**, 9759–9815 (2021).
- ¹⁴A. Jain, S. P. Ong, G. Hautier, W. Chen, W. D. Richards, S. Dacek, S. Cholia, D. Gunter, D. Skinner, G. Ceder, and K. A. Persson, “Commentary: The Materials Project: A materials genome approach to accelerating materials innovation,” *APL Materials* **1** (2013), 10.1063/1.4812323.
- ¹⁵C. Chen and S. P. Ong, “A universal graph deep learning interatomic potential for the periodic table,” *Nature Computational Science* **2**, 718–728 (2022).
- ¹⁶B. Deng, P. Zhong, K. Jun, J. Riebesell, K. Han, C. J. Bartel, and G. Ceder, “CHGNet as a pretrained universal neural network potential for charge-informed atomistic modelling,” *Nature Machine Intelligence* **5**, 1031–1041 (2023).
- ¹⁷A. Merchant, S. Batzner, S. S. Schoenholz, M. Aykol, G. Cheon, and E. D. Cubuk, “Scaling deep learning for materials discovery,” *Nature* , 1–6 (2023).
- ¹⁸S. Curtarolo, W. Setyawan, G. L. Hart, M. Jahnatek, R. V. Chepulskii, R. H. Taylor, S. Wang, J. Xue, K. Yang, O. Levy, M. J. Mehl, H. T. Stokes, D. O. Demchenko, and D. Morgan, “AFLOW: An automatic framework for high-throughput materials discovery,” *Computational Materials Science* **58**, 218–226 (2012).
- ¹⁹S. Kirklin, J. E. Saal, B. Meredig, A. Thompson, J. W. Doak, M. Aykol, S. Rühl, and C. Wolverton, “The Open Quantum Materials Database (OQMD): assessing the accuracy of DFT formation energies,” *npj Computational Materials* **1**, 15010 (2015).
- ²⁰C. Draxl and M. Scheffler, “The NOMAD laboratory: from data sharing to artificial intelligence,” *Journal of Physics: Materials* **2**, 036001 (2019).
- ²¹C. R. Groom, I. J. Bruno, M. P. Lightfoot, and S. C. Ward, “The Cambridge Structural Database,” *Acta Crystallographica Section B Structural Science, Crystal Engineering and Materials* **72**, 171–179 (2016).
- ²²B. Olsthoorn, R. M. Geilhufe, S. S. Borysov, and A. V. Balatsky, “Band Gap Prediction for Large Organic Crystal Structures with Machine Learning,” *Advanced Quantum Technologies* **2** (2019), 10.1002/qute.201900023.
- ²³S. S. Borysov, R. M. Geilhufe, and A. V. Balatsky, “Organic materials database: An open-access online database for data mining,” *PLOS ONE* **12**, 1–14 (2017).
- ²⁴J. Hellsvik, R. D. Pérez, R. M. Geilhufe, M. Månsson, and A. V. Balatsky, “Spin wave excitations of magnetic metalorganic materials,” *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **4**, 024409 (2020).
- ²⁵R. M. Geilhufe, B. Olsthoorn, and A. V. Balatsky, “Shifting computational boundaries for complex organic materials,” *Nature Physics* **17**, 152–154 (2021).
- ²⁶F. M. Paruzzo, A. Hofstetter, F. Musil, S. De, M. Ceriotti, and L. Emsley, “Chemical shifts in molecular solids by machine learning,” *Nature communications* **9**, 4501 (2018).
- ²⁷J. S. Smith, O. Isayev, and A. E. Roitberg, “Ani-1, a data set of 20 million calculated off-equilibrium conformations for organic molecules,” *Scientific data* **4**, 1–8 (2017).
- ²⁸J. S. Smith, O. Isayev, and A. E. Roitberg, “ANI-1: an extensible neural network potential with DFT accuracy at force field computational cost,” *Chemical Science* **8**, 3192–3203 (2017).
- ²⁹J. S. Smith, B. Nebgen, N. Lubbers, O. Isayev, and A. E. Roitberg, “Less is more: Sampling chemical space with active learning,” *The Journal of chemical physics* **148** (2018).
- ³⁰F. Musil, S. De, J. Yang, J. E. Campbell, G. M. Day, and M. Ceriotti, “Machine learning for the structure–energy–property landscapes of molecular crystals,” *Chemical Science* **9**, 1289–1300 (2018).
- ³¹V. Kapil and E. A. Engel, “A complete description of thermodynamic stabilities of molecular crystals,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **119** (2022), 10.1073/pnas.2111769119.
- ³²B. Mladineo and I. Lončarić, “Thermosalient phase transitions from machine learning interatomic potential,” *Zenodo* (2023), 10.5281/zenodo.10003578.
- ³³S. Wengert, G. Csányi, K. Reuter, and J. T. Margraf, “Data-efficient machine learning for molecular crystal structure prediction,” *Chemical Science* **12**, 4536–4546 (2021).
- ³⁴S. Wengert, G. Csányi, K. Reuter, and J. T. Margraf, “A Hybrid Machine Learning Approach for Structure Stability Prediction in Molecular Co-crystal Screenings,” *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **18**, 4586–4593 (2022).
- ³⁵J. Behler and M. Parrinello, “Generalized Neural-Network Representation of High-Dimensional Potential-Energy Surfaces,” *Physical Review Letters* **98**, 146401 (2007).
- ³⁶A. P. Bartók, M. C. Payne, R. Kondor, and G. Csányi, “Gaussian Approximation Potentials: The Accuracy of Quantum Mechanics, without the Electrons,” *Physical Review Letters* **104**, 136403 (2010).
- ³⁷I. Batatia, D. P. Kovacs, G. N. C. Simm, C. Ortner, and G. Csányi, “MACE: Higher Order Equivariant Message Passing Neural Networks for Fast and Accurate Force Fields,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, edited by A. H. Oh, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, and K. Cho (2022).
- ³⁸G. A. Dolgonos, J. Hoja, and A. D. Boese, “Revised values for the x23 benchmark set of molecular crystals,” *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **21**, 24333–24344 (2019).
- ³⁹J.-D. Chai and M. Head-Gordon, “Systematic optimization of long-range corrected hybrid density functionals,” *The Journal of chemical physics* **128** (2008).
- ⁴⁰R. Ditchfield, W. J. Hehre, and J. A. Pople, “Self-consistent molecular-orbital methods. ix. an extended gaussian-type basis for molecular-orbital studies of organic molecules,” *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **54**, 724–728 (1971).
- ⁴¹J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, and M. Ernzerhof, “Generalized gradient approximation made simple,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **77**, 3865–3868 (1996).
- ⁴²A. M. Reilly and A. Tkatchenko, “Understanding the role of vibrations, exact exchange, and many-body van der waals interactions in the cohesive properties of molecular crystals,” *The Journal of chemical physics* **139** (2013).

- ⁴³M. Ceriotti, G. A. Tribello, and M. Parrinello, "Demonstrating the transferability and the descriptive power of sketch-map," *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **9**, 1521–1532 (2013).
- ⁴⁴R. J. Campello, D. Moulavi, A. Zimek, and J. Sander, "Hierarchical density estimates for data clustering, visualization, and outlier detection," *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data (TKDD)* **10**, 1–51 (2015).
- ⁴⁵S. Batzner, A. Musaelian, L. Sun, M. Geiger, J. P. Mailoa, M. Kornbluth, N. Molinari, T. E. Smidt, and B. Kozinsky, "E (3)-equivariant graph neural networks for data-efficient and accurate interatomic potentials," *Nature communications* **13**, 2453 (2022).
- ⁴⁶C. Devereux, J. S. Smith, K. K. Huddleston, K. Barros, R. Zubatyuk, O. Isayev, and A. E. Roitberg, "Extending the applicability of the ani deep learning molecular potential to sulfur and halogens," *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **16**, 4192–4202 (2020).
- ⁴⁷A. Hjorth Larsen, J. Jørgen Mortensen, J. Blomqvist, I. E. Castelli, R. Christensen, M. Dułak, J. Friis, M. N. Groves, B. Hammer, C. Hargus, E. D. Hermes, P. C. Jennings, P. Bjerre Jensen, J. Kermode, J. R. Kitchin, E. Leonhard Kolsbjerg, J. Kubal, K. Kaasbjerg, S. Lysgaard, J. Bergmann Maronsson, T. Maxson, T. Olsen, L. Pastewka, A. Peterson, C. Rostgaard, J. Schiøtz, O. Schütt, M. Strange, K. S. Thygesen, T. Vegge, L. Vilhelmsen, M. Walter, Z. Zeng, and K. W. Jacobsen, "The atomic simulation environment—a Python library for working with atoms," *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **29**, 273002 (2017).
- ⁴⁸E. Caldeweyher, J.-M. Mewes, S. Ehlert, and S. Grimme, "Extension and evaluation of the D4 London-dispersion model for periodic systems," *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **22**, 8499–8512 (2020).
- ⁴⁹E. Caldeweyher, S. Ehlert, A. Hansen, H. Neugebauer, S. Spicher, C. Bannwarth, and S. Grimme, "A generally applicable atomic-charge dependent London dispersion correction," *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **150**, 154122 (2019).
- ⁵⁰J. Nyman, O. S. Pundyke, and G. M. Day, "Accurate force fields and methods for modelling organic molecular crystals at finite temperatures," *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **18**, 15828–15837 (2016).
- ⁵¹J. D. Gale, L. M. LeBlanc, P. R. Spackman, A. Silvestri, and P. Raiteri, "A universal force field for materials, periodic gfn-ff: Implementation and examination," *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **17**, 7827–7849 (2021).
- ⁵²J. Moellmann and S. Grimme, "Dft-d3 study of some molecular crystals," *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **118**, 7615–7621 (2014).
- ⁵³A. Otero-De-La-Roza and E. R. Johnson, "A benchmark for non-covalent interactions in solids," *The Journal of chemical physics* **137** (2012).
- ⁵⁴A. van der Lee and D. G. Dumitrescu, "Thermal expansion properties of organic crystals: a CSD study," *Chemical Science* **12**, 8537–8547 (2021).
- ⁵⁵J. Hoja, A. M. Reilly, and A. Tkatchenko, "First-principles modeling of molecular crystals: structures and stabilities, temperature and pressure," *WIREs Computational Molecular Science* **7** (2017), 10.1002/wcms.1294.
- ⁵⁶A. Kadan, K. Ryczko, A. Wildman, R. Wang, A. Roitberg, and T. Yamazaki, "Accelerated organic crystal structure prediction with genetic algorithms and machine learning," *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **19**, 9388–9402 (2023).